

Integrated nonlinear multi-scale material modelling of fiber reinforced plastics with Digimat – Pressure and rate-dependent material behaviours.

Laurent ADAM, Samuel MELCHIOR and Marc DUFLOT

MSC Software Belgium
Axis Park – Building H. 9, Rue Emile Francqui
B-1435 Mont-Saint-Guibert. Belgium.
Laurent.Adam@e-xstream.com – www.e-xstream.com

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The simulation of composites has to address several challenges: anisotropic behavior following the local microstructure, nonlinear behaviors (pressure dependent plasticity, rate sensitivity, temperature and moisture sensitivity ...), various failure mechanisms, ... Predicting such nonlinear behaviors from constituents behaviors and composite microstructure is key in order to address challenges of material and structural engineering. Indeed material engineers are requesting analysis methods allowing them to link microstructure to effective properties. FE analysts on their side wants to describe composite designs in complex load scenarios which require the usage of advanced material and failure models. To model the local anisotropic behavior, the analyses must take into account the real material microstructure as predicted by process modeling software (injection or compression molding for short fiber reinforcement; draping or thermo-forming in the case of UD or woven composites). All this must be available in a smooth and effective workflow and cover various types of scenarios and question, from simple stress analysis over the investigation of crash behavior or full life time prediction for the plastic composite part.

This paper deals especially with the modeling of pressure sensitive plastic behavior as well as rate dependent elastic and plastic deformation regimes (i.e. viscoelasticity-viscoplasticity) through the use of nonlinear homogenization scheme.

Such modeling is performed by using Digimat which aims at bridging the gap between process and structural modeling by building nonlinear multi-scale material models, using the local material microstructure, in order to predict different kind of performances. The technology developed in Digimat (see for example [1,2,3]) as well as representative applications will also be covered in the paper.

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